

D4.4: Initial Report on Good Practices

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Executive summary

This document is a deliverable (D4.4 *Initial Report on Good Practices*) of the ARIADNE project (“Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe”), which is funded under the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme. D4.4 is associated with WP4, which is titled *Good Practices and Dissemination*, which is focussed on the dissemination of project outcomes and to inform and create a wider community of good practice. D4.4 reports the results of Task 4.5 *Good Practices*, and involved the identification, assessment and definition of good practices in archaeological research activities, potentially affecting the use of the ARIADNE research infrastructure, to include:

- Survey of current good practices related to the use of existing infrastructures
- Assessment, adaptation and customisation of such practices
- Guidance on applications, including examples
- Reference information

Within these areas, particular themes were explored, including:

- GIS, archaeological prospection and related datasets
- Scientific data organisation and related datasets
- Applications of visualisation technologies in archaeology and related datasets
- Semantics and metadata

The main objective of D4.4 is to describe and assess the nature of good practice in use by the content providing ARIADNE partners, and to list contributions to the Guides to Good Practice by these partners, planned for completion by the end of the project. The contributions identified in D4.4 will form the basis for work to be carried out under Task 4.6, *Guides to Good Practice*, and will be reported in D4.6. A survey of the ARIADNE content providing partners was carried out, which highlighted a diverse range of guidance and Good Practice. Good Practice usually takes the form of guidance documents, which reflect the partner's areas of expertise and function, and range from:

- Broad guidelines on data and report structures and the structure of national databases
- Guidelines and recommendations for excavation and fieldwork
- Guidelines for specific survey (e.g. lidar) or data set types (e.g. 3D or dating techniques)

In some cases these guidelines tie into wider guidance (e.g. CIDOC CRM) or good practice projects such as ArchaeoLandscapes or 3D-ICONS. This report identified five broad themes that will form the basis for work to be carried out under Task 4.6 *Guides to Good Practice*, these are:

- The alignment with, and referencing of, existing Good Practice documents
- The creation of case studies illustrating the application of Good Practice documents to specific data sets for which no good practice currently exists
- The referencing and incorporation of guidelines currently under production through the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D-ICONS projects into existing guidelines and the illustration of these guidelines through relevant case studies
- The revision, creation or enhancement of guidelines for 3D datasets
- The creation of guidelines for data from scientific dating and analysis, specifically dendrochronological datasets

Introduction

1.1 Objectives

Within WP4, Task 4.5 *Good Practices* involved the identification, assessment and definition of good practices in archaeological research activities, potentially affecting the use of the ARIADNE research infrastructure.

The specific objectives associated with Task 4.5 *Good Practices* are:

- survey of current good practices related to the use of existing infrastructures
- assessment, adaptation and customisation of such practices
- guidance on applications, including examples
- reference information

Within these areas, particular themes were explored, including:

- GIS, archaeological prospection and related datasets
- scientific data organisation and related datasets
- applications of visualisation technologies in archaeology and related datasets
- semantics and metadata

Areas of interest identified in Task 4.5 form the basis for work carried out under Task 4.6, *Guides to Good Practice*, and reported in D4.6.

1.2 The Role of Task 4.5 within ARIADNE

WP4 Good Practices and Dissemination combines the tasks required for communicating information about the ARIADNE project, with the work on Good Practices. These areas have been combined because it is not only important to understand the nature of Good Practices for and within the network, but to also make that information freely available to the domain. The main focus of Task 4.5 is to survey and understand the nature of Good Practices currently in use by the content providing partners. This is critical to understanding how archaeological data is created, used and stored by the partners, so as to inform the way this data can best be incorporated into the ARIADNE infrastructure. At the same time, it also allows the ARIADNE project to make an important assessment of how archaeological data is handled across Europe in terms of best practice. While this assessment is limited to the partners providing data to ARIADNE, and cannot be considered comprehensive, it forms a place to start. From this beginning, very general differences and similarities of practice can now be defined, and are thus reported in this deliverable.

In addition to beginning to define Good Practice within the ARIADNE project, content providing partners have been asked to contribute to the existing, formal Guides to Good Practice (the history of which is detailed below). This will allow the Guides to be expanded according the partner's areas of expertise, so that European approaches to Good Practice are better represented. This work is ongoing throughout the ARIADNE project, and will be reported as it progresses, either within this deliverable or its successor. These contributions will further aid archaeological researchers with expanded or updated sections within the existing guides, taking into account European practice, and further case studies highlighting European examples. This will represent another important resource and contribution to the domain from the ARIADNE project as a whole.

1.3 Background – A Brief History of the Guides to Good Practice

This section highlights the history of work undertaken by the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) to produce a set of Guides to Good Practice¹ focussed on documenting and preserving data created through archaeological research.

In addition to its core role as a digital archive, ADS also has a responsibility to promote standards and provide guidance in best practice in the creation, description, preservation and use of archaeological information and technical advice to the research community. In 1998 it published the first two publications in a series of Guides to Good Practice covering *Aerial Photography and Remote Sensing Data* and *GIS*. Subsequently, four guides looking at excavation and geophysical datasets, CAD, and virtual reality were published between 1998-2002 and all drew together key authors and contributors to produce widely relevant guidance in applying recognised standards for the creation, preservation, and re-use of digital resources. The original guides sat within a much larger cross-disciplinary series of Guides to Good Practice published by the Arts and Humanities Data Service (AHDS)², of which the ADS was then part. These guides have become widely used, cited, and endorsed by a number of key archaeological bodies in the UK including English Heritage and the Council for British Archaeology.

In 2006 ADS undertook the Big Data Project, funded by English Heritage, to look specifically at the practical issues raised in storing and disseminating large 3D datasets through three case studies covering marine survey, laser scanning, and Lidar data. The project included a data audit alongside a questionnaire survey and workshop aimed at 'big data' creators and produced a final report providing guidance in terms of both policy and practice for creating, storing, and accessing 'big data'. The project report also provided a key set of recommendations for future research which have subsequently informed the recent Guides to Good Practice project³.

Additionally, ADS involvement in the 2006-9 FP6 VENUS project⁴ also looked at the preservation of large, complex marine survey datasets and the key role that data selection plays in producing robust and reusable digital archives. While the VENUS project aimed to develop scientific methodologies and tools for the virtual exploration of underwater sites, the ADS role focussed on the long term preservation of the project's digital outputs and resulted in the publication of a VENUS Guide to Good Practice alongside an exemplar digital archive⁵. As with the Big Data Project, the VENUS project made a significant contribution to the subsequent revision and expansion of the Guides to Good Practice through the development of elements of the VENUS guide into a new general guide looking at marine survey data⁶.

In 2009, and with the support from the Andrew Mellon Foundation, the ADS began working with Digital Antiquity (tDAR) partners in the United States at the University of Arkansas and at Arizona State University on a collaborative project to revise and extend the previous series of guides. In addition to updating the content from the original six guides, the new project covered marine survey – building on the VENUS project guide – and terrestrial remote sensing, as well as laser scanning and close range photogrammetry. A key element of the new project was the integration and restructuring of existing guidance so that common generic sections from the old guides were combined with new material to form new 'guide-wide' sections covering elements such as archival strategies, project level metadata, copyright and archive deposition.

¹ <http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk>

² <http://www.ahds.ac.uk/>

³ http://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/propylaeumdok/volltexte/2010/497/pdf/06_04_austin_et_al_bigdata.pdf

⁴ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/VENUS_Toc

⁵ http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archives/view/venus_eu_2009/

⁶ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/RSMarine_Toc

The merging and restructuring process, aside from ensuring a homogenous and comprehensive set of new guidelines, also allowed an integrated workflow structure, with greater linking between common themes and elements between each guide or data type. The idea of a 'complete workflow' also allowed easy identification and variation of specific parts of the new guidelines, such as required deposit formats and metadata, to fit with the requirements of both the ADS and tDAR repositories. To allow the future community updating of the Guides they were also transferred to a wiki format.

Moreover, the current Guides also incorporate and revise a number of existing ADS project reports and working documents. Results and reports from projects such as the Big Data Project⁷ (looking at large datasets such as 3D and survey data) and the VENUS project⁸ (focussed on marine survey data) have provided studies of new types of data, often from outside the UK, upon which guidance and procedures have been created. The revision of the Guides has also allowed the incorporation of a number of ADS internal 'data procedure' documents thereby incorporating into the guides ingest and archiving procedures of what could be considered 'core' or common file types such as text documents, spreadsheets, databases, images, digital audio and digital video.

As well as more formal revision of procedures, the ACE ('Archaeology in Contemporary Europe') project provided a number of placements during 2012 which allowed students and professionals from Sweden, Greece, France, the Netherlands, and Poland to visit the ADS and receive training in digital archiving. A key component of the bursary was the application by the placement holder of ADS archiving procedures (specifically the Guides) to a dataset from their parent institution. The process of applying ADS archiving procedures to a familiar dataset allowed the bursary holder to familiarise themselves with the archiving procedure while also highlighting the applicability of ADS procedures to data outside of their usual geographic remit. This process proved to be valuable exercise and a number of case studies were produced and incorporated into the Guides to Good Practice⁹.

1.4 Discussion

As highlighted in Section 1.3, the current Guides to Good Practice have developed over a number of years, have evolved from separate hard-copy publications to an online collaborative resource, and have incorporated input from specialists in both the UK and, later, in the US. ARIADNE Tasks 4.5 and 4.6 allow a logical progression of this development through the involvement of new partners and with the identification of new areas of expertise and guidance.

As a result of the most recent phase of Guides revision involving partners based largely in the US, the opportunity to further explore and develop guidance through a variety of European partners is seen as clearly beneficial. The variety and history of archaeological practice in Europe is clear from the individual organisational reports presented in Section 2. When combined with the variety of organisations involved in Tasks 4.5 and 4.6, both in terms of size and remit, the partners provide both a broad resource and test bed for the development and application of good practice guidance across a range of archaeological practice.

⁷ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/research/bigData>

⁸ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/research/venus>

⁹ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/CS_CaseStudiesToc

2 Report on Best Practice and Areas of Expertise

This section consists of individual reports, organised by partner organisation, outlining specific areas of expertise and good practice work, proposed areas of contribution to Task 4.6, and areas where individual organisations feel that they would benefit from good practice documents and procedures.

Each report provides a brief description and history of the organisation before detailing current areas of expertise, available guidelines, and good practice. These elements, alongside proposed areas of contribution and areas where they feel development is required, are summarised in a table at the start of the report.

The major themes that emerge from these individual reports are subsequently discussed in Section 3 of this report. Section 4 then proceeds to allocate these themes to discrete areas of contribution for the Guides to Good Practice (Task 4.6). In summary, while a number of partner organisations such as ADS, DAI, and DANS have developed generic good practice guides on file formats and metadata standards to inform the preservation and future re-use of archaeological data, for other partners ‘best practice’ reflects their procedures for undertaking specific areas of archaeological fieldwork or research, or simply reflect the design of recording systems such as databases.

2.1 ADS (UK)

Areas of Expertise

Digital archiving and dissemination, metadata standards.

Relevant Good Practice work

ADS Guides to Good Practice

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Alignment and referencing of existing Guides with partner organisations
- Identification of suitable areas for case studies

Areas where Good Practice work required

Preservation and dissemination of virtual reality and 3D datasets

The Archaeology Data Service (ADS), based at the University of York, was established in 1996 to collect and preserve digital resources created as a product of archaeological research, and to promote and disseminate this data freely online. The ADS works with national and local archaeological agencies, and research councils involved in the funding of archaeological research, to negotiate deposition of project data. This includes data derived from fieldwork as well as desk-based studies. The types of data involved include: text reports, databases, images, digitised maps and plans, numerical datasets related to topographical and sub-surface surveys and other locational data, as well as reconstruction drawings.

In addition to its core role as archive, the ADS also has a responsibility to promote standards and guidelines for best practice in the creation, description, preservation and use of archaeological information and providing technical advice to the research community.

ADS have provided information in the following areas of expertise and Good Practice:

Guides to Good Practice

Since 1998 the ADS has published a number of Guides to Good Practice documents covering a range of data types and techniques and focussed on data documentation and preservation. Six guides covering Aerial Photography and Remote Sensing Data, GIS, Excavation and Fieldwork archives,

geophysical survey, CAD, and virtual reality were published by the ADS during the period 1998-2002. During 2009-2011 the ADS, together with Digital Antiquity in the United States, undertook a collaborative project to revise and extend the previous series of guides, update the content from these original publications and expand this to cover additional subjects such as marine and terrestrial remote sensing, laser scanning, and close range photogrammetry alongside generic elements such as archival strategies, project level metadata, copyright and archive deposition. The background and history of the ADS Guides to Good Practice are discussed in more detail in Section 1.3.

Advice for Depositors

In addition to the general Guides to Good Practice, ADS uses Guidelines for Depositors¹⁰ that are specific to ADS ingest and preservation procedures. These guidelines outline the requirements, in terms of files formats and metadata, that ADS specify for those wishing to deposit data.

These in turn fit into a wider framework of ADS guidance documents that cover data deposition and dissemination. These include:

- The ADS Collections Policy¹¹
- Guidance on the Deposition of Sensitive Digital Data¹²
- Guidance on the Selection of Material for Deposit and Archive¹³

Repository Operations

The ADS also follow and make publicly available a number of documents, which outline how, as an archive, the ADS deal with and secure digital datasets. These documents include:

- ADS Ingest Manual¹⁴
- ADS Preservation Policy¹⁵
- ADS Repository Operations¹⁶

Many of these documents have been made available in support of the Data Seal of Approval (discussed below, Section 2.7), awarded to ADS in 2010¹⁷ (renewed 2013).

Data Procedures

As well as publicly available guidelines, ADS also have a number of internal data procedure documents covering data migration and documentation. These follow widely accepted approaches to the use and adoption of metadata and file formats as recommended by organisations such as the Digital Preservation Coalition¹⁸ and the Digital Curation Centre¹⁹.

¹⁰ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/guidelinesForDepositors>

¹¹ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/collectionsPolicy>

¹² <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/sensitiveDataPolicy>

¹³ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/advice/selectionGuidance>

¹⁴ http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/attach/preservation/ADS_ingest_manual_V2.pdf

¹⁵ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/attach/preservation/PreservationPolicyV1.3.1.pdf>

¹⁶ http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/attach/preservation/ADS_Repository_Operations_V2.pdf

¹⁷ https://assessment.datasealofapproval.org/assessment_36/seal/html/

¹⁸ <http://www.dpconline.org/>

¹⁹ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/>

2.2 ARHEO (Romania)

Areas of Expertise

3D field documentation, surveying and remote sensing investigations.

Relevant Good Practice work

Arheovest has developed its own method of fieldwork and diagnostic of survey results based on national indicators, necessities in the field and accumulated experience.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Input regarding remote sensing data, surveying, 3D documentation and related metadata.
- ARHEO are continuously conducting remote sensing (magnetometer) surveys combined with topographic surveys and photogrammetry. ARHEO would like to share expertise, improve methods, and collaborate in a wider framework of field surveys.
- Possible case study focussed on data from Banat region.

Areas where Good Practice work required

Description of archaeological sites, rescue excavations, integration of archaeological work at national level.

ARHEO, the Asociația Arheo Vest Timisoara (English translation: Arheovest Association Timisoara), was founded in 2006, and its main activities focus on the research and protection of archaeological heritage in the Banat region. Arheovest also aims to promote archaeology and archaeological findings to both public and scientific communities and provides training and specialisation for students and archaeology enthusiasts in the domain of interdisciplinary archaeology.

A non-governmental organisation, Arheovest consists of members from a variety of backgrounds including archaeology, history, geography, ethnography, computer science, architecture, cartography, law, and mass media.

ARHEO has provided information on the following areas of expertise and good practice:

ARHEO follows a number of top-level guidelines and legislation regarding the undertaking of archaeological fieldwork and the recording of archaeology (laws, ordinances, codes of conduct, etc.). These are described on the Arheovest website²⁰ (Romanian language only). In addition, a number of generic guidelines are also available from the Romanian Institute for National Heritage²¹.

In terms of good practice Arheovest, as a Romanian association, also follows a number of recording guidelines created by cImeC, the Romanian Institute for Cultural Memory. These guidelines can be found in the Methodology section of the cImeC website²².

Generally these guidelines are aimed at the recording of physical objects/mobile heritage and are largely aimed at museums. Specific examples incorporating wider good practice work include template forms (and instructions) based on the CIDOC standard²³. The DOCPAT program²⁴ has also been developed to track museum archive collections and provides a structure, based on the CIDOC forms, for recording various types of archive and collection.

Two online systems also provide a framework for the recording and dissemination of archaeological fieldwork data in Romania:

²⁰ <http://www.arheovest.com/legislation.html>

²¹ <http://www.patrimoniu.ro/ro/>

²² <http://cimec.ro/Metodologie/Metodologie.html>

²³ <http://cimec.ro/Metodologie/Formulare-Evidenta-Clasarea-Pat-Mobil.html>

²⁴ <http://cimec.ro/Metodologie/Programul-DOCPAT.html>

ACERA²⁵ (Administration System for Archaeological Research in Romania) is an online system focussed on uniting and streamlining the application, funding, and authorisation of fieldwork together with the reporting of research results. The system covers both fieldwork and research projects and allows tiered and restricted access to datasets for both public and professional users. The system is described in more detail on the ACERA website²⁶.

The National Heritage Institute eGISpat system²⁷ is an ESRI-based GIS that has been designed to inform decision-making in the management, restoration, conservation and recovery of immovable heritage. The system incorporates multiple types of data (both spatial and non-spatial data).

²⁵ <http://acera.cimec.ro/>

²⁶ <http://acera.cimec.ro/DespreAcera.aspx>

²⁷ <http://egispat.inp.org.ro/>

2.3 ARUP-CAS (Czech Republic)

Areas of Expertise

Data management, aerial photography.

Relevant Good Practice work

Software systems and guidelines for data management.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Possible involvement in environmental data guidelines
- Input into aerial photography / survey data guidelines

Areas where Good Practice work required

A Guide to good practice for collecting and analysing environmental samples.

The Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences in the Czech Republic (ARUP-CAS) is a research institution focussing on prehistoric, medieval and modern archaeology. The Institute focuses on obtaining and analysing new archaeological resources, the development of archaeological theory, methodology and informatics, and archaeological heritage management. The Institute plays a specific role within the field of archaeological heritage management and maintains the largest archaeological library in the Czech Republic.

The Institute is formally responsible for the quality of field-work undertaken in the Czech Republic and operates as a central archive for reports from all field activities in Bohemia. In addition to storing such material, the Institute sets a structure and defines the contents of such excavation reports. The Institute has specific interest and expertise in aerial photography, geophysics, archaeological survey, and the digitisation of archives. The institute is also actively involved in geoarchaeology and bioarchaeology, e.g. archeogenetics, paleobotany or paleopathology.

Data Management

ARUP-CAS maintains a number of software applications, which are used to collect and manage archaeological datasets deposited by archaeologists in Bohemia, but occasionally from the whole Czech Republic. These applications include both glossaries and data structures and can therefore, in a sense, be understood as providing 'guides to the best practice' in terms of structuring and organising information from field activities.

The software / information systems currently held by ARUP-CAS include:

- Archaeological database of Bohemia
- Digital archives of the Institute of Archaeology, Prague
- Database of documents prepared for the Digital archives of the IA
- Internet database (registration) of archaeological field activities
- Map of the archaeological documentation point within the historic centre of Prague

It is the intention that all of these applications (plus the Bibliography of Czech Archaeology) will be included in a complex information system called the "Archaeological map of the Czech Republic" which should be finished in about two years.

In addition to the systems themselves, detailed user manuals are also available to be downloaded online (Czech language only)²⁸.

²⁸ <https://cas-cz.academia.edu/MartinKuna/Archaeological-Informatics>

Arches

ARUP-CAS has also been involved as a project partner in Arches (Archaeological Resources in Cultural Heritage: a European Standard)²⁹, a two-year project which has looked to produce a guide to best practice for archaeological archiving in Europe. The primary output of Arches is a best practice manual, which is freely available to download in a number of languages³⁰.

²⁹ <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/arches/>

³⁰

<http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/arches/Wiki.jsp?page=The%20Standard%20and%20Guide%20to%20Best%20Practice%20in%20Archaeological%20Archiving%20in%20Europe>

2.4 ATHENA-CETI (Greece)

Areas of Expertise

Scientific analysis and dating methods, 3D digitisation

Relevant Good Practice work

Internal procedural guidelines for sample processing

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Thermoluminescence/ceramic analysis guide
- Input into Dendrochronology guide
- Input into 3D modelling guides

Areas where Good Practice work required

Thermoluminescence/ceramic analysis guide

The Cultural and Educational Technology Institute (CETI) was founded in 1998 in Xanthi as an independent research institute under the auspices of the General Secretariat for Research and Technology, Ministry of Development. In November 2003 it was integrated into the Centre of Integrated Research for the Information Society (IRIS), which on February 2006 was renamed Athena – Research and Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies (Athena R.C.). In the beginning of March 2012 CETI was merged with Athena’s Institute of Language and Speech Processing (ILSP) and now operates as a division of the new Institute.

The objective of the Cultural and Education Technology Institute is to strengthen research and technological activities and the application of new technologies in culture, humanities, and education.

More specifically, CETI is focusing its research activities in the following categories:

- Application of Information Technology in the study, preservation, and dissemination of cultural heritage with major points of interest the works of art, monuments and artefacts
- Laboratory study of related material, particularly ceramics
- Application of information technology in the area of Education, with a particular interest in cultural and industrial education

Special attention is given to the area of culture heritage, where the application of scientific techniques in the study and research of archaeological problems demands specially trained staff and advanced technology, which supplies the requested expertise for the study, archiving, preservation, presentation, dissemination, age determination, analyses and investigation of manufacturing patterns of archaeological findings regardless of their present location as museum objects or in archaeological sites.

CETI currently uses a number of internal good practice guidelines and protocols for the processing of samples and the subsequent extraction of scientific data (e.g. Figure 1). The main focus of these documents and protocols is procedural; ensuring the credibility, accuracy and completeness of the resulting data in order to optimize subsequent exploitation (e.g. dating, provenance, etc.). Although these guidelines document processing they do not make any specifications in terms of either structure or storage of the resulting datasets.

The specific techniques in which CETI identifies as areas of expertise are:

- **X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF)**, used in the qualitative and quantitative determination of the chemical composition of solid or liquid samples. The CETI lab primarily uses this technique for archaeometric purposes, i.e., the determination of the elemental

composition of (mainly) ceramics (without excluding other materials as well) in provenance studies. In addition, it can also give valuable information about the raw materials used, not only for the clay body, but also in paintings and/or slips of decorated pottery. It should be noted that it is a non-destructive technique.

- **Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)**, used for the quantitative determination of the concentration of specific inorganic elements in archaeological samples. The technique is complementary to XRF in that XRF allows you to "get an idea" of what inorganic elements are present in the samples, while AAS provides the concentrations of each element with high accuracy. It is mainly used to quantitatively determine the "trace" elements (elements of very low concentration, where XRF displays large errors). Unfortunately, it is a destructive technique (sample is digested with acids).
- **Thermoluminescence (TL)** and **Optically Stimulation Luminescence (OSL)**, both techniques are primarily employed for dating ceramics.
- **Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)**, for the production of images of ceramic samples (without excluding other materials) allowing the in-depth observation of their structure and of other details in order to ascertain the production method of ceramic objects from one area to other.
- **Energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)**. Based on the same principles as XRF, this technique is used in conjunction with SEM to provide data on the chemical composition of specific areas of a sample.

Figure 1. Protocol for the dating of ceramics with thermoluminescence.

CETI, through Clepsydra (Centre for the Digitisation of Cultural Heritage)³¹, also undertakes the 3D digitisation of objects and monuments for the archiving, preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage. Clepsydra provides a number of integrated approaches to both 2D and 3D digitisation including 3D laser scanning for large (monument) and small objects, photogrammetry, and other photographic techniques such as modelling from structured light.

CETI also participates in various on-going and past projects related to Heritage Sciences, such as STACHEM³² where it contributed the charting of scientific and technical resources such as laboratories of applied chemistry and physics for archaeology in the Eastern Mediterranean, and to the development of the regional strategic plan for RIs concerning archaeological sciences and digital heritage. CETI also contributes to 3D-ICONS where it is involved in the creation of 3D models of a series of internationally important monuments and buildings in the area of Greece and will contribute this content to Europeana.

Finally, CETI is seeking to inform and train new scientists from various disciplines through seminars and interdisciplinary lectures in archaeological and archaeometric topics, and provides information on best practices and procedures related to the use of laboratory measurements in archaeology and the interpretation of their results, as well as the creation, recording, and storage of excavation datasets.

³¹ <http://clepsydra.ipet.gr/index.php?lang=en>

³² <http://www.cyi.ac.cy/stachem-overview.html>

2.5 CYI-STARC (Cyprus)

Areas of Expertise

3D datasets, visualisation, metadata and repositories.

Relevant Good Practice work

3D repository development including metadata, schema and file formats.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Recommendations for the creation of 3D repositories and associated metadata.
- Guidance on 3D file formats (e.g. 3D PDF and X3D) and dissemination

Areas where Good Practice work required

Regulations regarding registration of archaeological and heritage sites by governmental institutions, systematic surveys of the island and rescue excavations.

The Science and Technology in Archaeology Research Center (STARC) of The Cyprus Institute participates in a wide range of national and international collaborative research focussed on the development, introduction and use of advanced science and technologies in the field of archaeology, cultural heritage and history of the region. This research encompasses a number of themes and includes visualisation and imaging, scientific analysis, and digital libraries.

STARC have provided information on the following areas of expertise and good practice:

STARC Repository

As a creator of 3D data, STARC maintains a 3D repository to hold the data from its projects. The main scope of the STARC Repository³³ is to serve as a research platform for the further development of metadata, including how to create repositories of 3D data, and how to create various tools for the interaction with digital content. The STARC Repository is also developing an XML metadata schema as the basis for the repository. While not explicitly recommending specific formats, the STARC Repository also currently employs 3D PDF and X3D formats for data dissemination.

Participation in related projects:

3D-ICONS

The Cyprus Institute provides 3D content of iconic heritage sites in Cyprus and abroad (e.g. Italy and Israel) and its related documentation data (text info, images, etc.). It also provides input on developing the 3D-icons metadata schema, an extension of the CARARE schema for documenting 3D cultural heritage content.

ArchaeoLandscapes

The role of the Cyprus Institute within the ArchaeoLandscapes project is to perform a survey on existing archives of aerial photos related to archaeological research, propose a metadata schema that describes these archives, and look for solutions for improving accessibility to them. It also promotes research in 3D documentation of archaeological excavations and alignment of such research with remote sensing.

³³ <http://public.cyi.ac.cy/starcRepo/>

2.6 DAI (Germany)

Areas of Expertise

Data archiving, metadata.

Relevant Good Practice work

IANUS and DARIAH-DE Guidelines, input into ArchaeoLandscapes project.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Alignment, referencing and translation between the IANUS Recommendations and ADS Guides to Good Practice.
- Input into the Dendrochronology guide.

Areas where Good Practice work required

Alignment and referencing between ADS and IANUS guidelines.

The DAI (Deutsche Archäologische Institut / German Archaeological Institute) is a federal agency under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs consisting of a number of international or subject-specific departments. The Institute undertakes fieldwork and research and also maintains archives, libraries, and laboratories. The Institute also has a dedicated Division for ICT, which deals not only with infrastructure but also with data creation, digitisation, and processing.

DAI have provided information on the following projects that highlight their areas of expertise and best practice:

- IANUS
- DARIAH-DE
- ArchaeoLandscapes

IANUS

The IANUS project, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG), aims to create a German national research data centre focussed on Archaeology and Classical Studies. Alongside details of the work packages being undertaken during the project, the IANUS project website³⁴ (German language only) outlines an extensive set of IT Recommendations^{35 36} for the creation and preservation of research data. Previous (internal only) IT guidelines for all DAI departments did exist but these have now been replaced by the IANUS IT Recommendations. These recommendations, while created specifically for DAI, have featured ADS input and can be seen as a German-language parallel to the ADS Guides to Good Practice.

As with the ADS Guides to Good Practice, the DAI IT Recommendations adopt a project lifecycle approach to data documentation and preservation that starts during the project planning and data creation stages and subsequently deals with documentation and metadata, file management and storage, data selection, and data access. File formats are dealt with in detail by data type (e.g. databases, GIS, 3D data, and text documents, amongst others) with preferred file formats specified alongside the metadata to be recorded.

³⁴ <http://www.ianus-fdz.de/>

³⁵ <http://www.ianus-fdz.de/it-empfehlungen/>

³⁶ The full list of contents can be seen here: <http://www.ianus-fdz.de/it-empfehlungen/?q=node/1>

In parallel to - and expanding upon - the file formats section, the Research Methods section³⁷ of the IT Recommendations deals with the output from various research methodologies (e.g. Geophysics, Archaeobotany, Dendrochronology, etc.) in terms of the types of data created, the methods of processing used, types of metadata used, and case studies created. Although currently still a work in progress, this section looks to provide, for each methodology, a detailed introduction to the data created by each research method alongside guidelines and recommendation for preserving and documenting the specific outputs.

As of the date of this report, the IANUS IT Recommendations are still in the process of being written.

DARIAH-DE

DAI involvement in the DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) project produced a number of general guideline documents applicable to humanities subjects (German language). These documents sit at a more general level than the IANUS Recommendations, but again focus both on the creation of research data and its appropriate management. A document looking at subject-specific recommendations for data and metadata ('Fachspezifische Empfehlungen für Daten und Metadaten'³⁸) was produced by DAI under DARIAH and acts as a signpost document largely focussed on metadata and controlled vocabularies. The archaeology-specific section³⁹ recommends a wide range of existing metadata schema such as MIDAS Heritage, LIDO, and CIDOC-CRM.

In addition, DAI has also been involved in the production of two DARIAH e-publication Working Papers. The first, 'Interdisciplinary Interoperability', (in English) is focussed, as the title suggests, on interdisciplinary interoperability of data⁴⁰. While largely an assessment of protocol and schema technologies such as REST, Atom, OAI-PMH, RDF, and SKOS, this document also highlights the application of various general / high-level metadata schemas (e.g. Dublin Core) alongside persistent identifiers (PURL and URN) and identifiers for place names and subjects (e.g. TGN, DDC, LCSH). The second Working Paper ('Datenlizenzen für geisteswissenschaftliche Forschungsdaten - Rechtliche Bedingungen und Handlungsbedarf'⁴¹, German language only) focuses on the licensing and copyright basics relevant to humanities research data. This document covers metadata, images, and databases and includes a Licencing Decision tool and licencing case studies from ADS and DANS.

Additionally with DARIAH, DAI is currently involved in a work package, conducted by partners from the Netherlands, France, and Ireland, looking specifically at 'Best Practices and Open Access' and which aims to create guidance and reference materials for specific research communities to openly disseminate and access - as well as preserve - research and data. The work package will include the creation of a number of user case studies to provide models for those creating data e.g. advice for individuals with personal archives, academics creating funded research archives, and so on. This work will continue until 2016.

ArchaeoLandscapes

DAI is also involved in the ArchaeoLandscapes EU-project which is committed to promoting the pan-European exchange of skills and understanding about remote sensing techniques and landscape studies. In addition to workshops, training and exhibitions guides, a recent guide to aerial archaeology edited by Chris Musson, Rog Palmer and Stefano Campana has been published^{42 43} and a further guide on geophysical techniques in archaeology by Armin Schmidt.

³⁷ <http://www.ianus-fdz.de/it-empfehlungen/?q=node/6>

³⁸ <http://dev2.dariah.eu/wiki/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=20058160>

³⁹ <http://dev2.dariah.eu/wiki/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=20058856>

⁴⁰ <http://resolver.sub.uni-goettingen.de/purl/?dariah-2014-1>

⁴¹ <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:gbv:7-dariah-2014-4-8>

⁴² <http://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/propylaeumdok/volltexte/2013/2009>

⁴³ <http://www.univie.ac.at/aarg/php/cms/Occasional-Publications/>

2.7 DANS (The Netherlands)

Areas of Expertise

- Data archiving including metadata standards, file formats (preferred formats, accepted formats, file format migrations), and data organisation in online Data management and archiving System DANS EASY
- Repository assessment and certification (Data Seal of Approval)
- The TRiDAS data standard for dendrochronology

Relevant Good Practice work

- Data deposit guidelines⁴⁴;
- Data processing protocol;
- Preferred Formats guide;
- Data citing guidelines using Persistent Identifiers;
- Data Seal of Approval repository assessment and certification;
- Research Data Selection guidelines⁴⁵;
- Data Management Plan for managing, documenting and sharing data⁴⁶
- The TRiDAS data standard for dendrochronology.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

Dendrochronology Guide. Personnel: Prof. Esther Jansma (head of the DCCD Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology); Peter Brewer (Research Associate at the Center for Mediterranean Archaeology and the Environment, University of Arizona).

Areas where Good Practice work required

Creation of Dendrochronology Guide.

DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services), an institute of KNAW (The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences) and NWO (The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research), have provided information on the following areas of good practice and expertise:

- Data archiving including metadata standards, file format standards and data organisation as used with the self-depositing Electronic Archiving System DANS EASY
- Repository assessment and certification (Data Seal of Approval)
- The TRiDAS data standard for dendrochronology

DANS EASY

The DANS website⁴⁷ promotes sustained access to digital research data via the EASY system, DANS' online Electronic Archiving System for research data, and provides guidance on how data should be deposited and documented. The website and accompanying documentation is available in both Dutch and English.

The EASY online system allows for the automated deposit of data into the DANS digital archive by data providers. A factsheet⁴⁸ titled 'Your 7 steps to sustainable data' briefly outlines the data

⁴⁴ <http://www.edna.nl/documentatie.html>

⁴⁵ <http://www.dans.knaw.nl/content/categorieen/publicaties/dans-studies-digital-archiving-6>

⁴⁶ <http://www.dans.knaw.nl/en/node/1964>

⁴⁷ <http://www.dans.knaw.nl/en/content/data-archive/depositing-data>

⁴⁸

<http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/factsheets/Factsheet%20Your%207%20steps%20to%20sustainable%20data%20DEF.pdf>

preparation and deposit process while providing links to other useful resources containing more detail.

A number of PDF documents linked from the ‘Depositing data’ page provide detailed discipline-specific deposit guidelines for data from Archaeology, History, Language and Literature Studies, Life Sciences and Medicine, Social and Behavioural Sciences, and ‘Other Disciplines’. These documents provide a detailed, illustrated, step-by-step run through of the deposit process (via EASY) and focus largely on the completion of the online metadata forms that document the deposited data. The documents additionally provide information on data selection and on the creation of both file and data documentation/metadata.

A separate ‘preferred formats’ PDF document⁴⁹ provides a concise tabulated overview of the file formats that should be used when depositing datasets with DANS. This document lists both preferred formats (i.e. those which are seen by DANS as stable and best suited for long-term preservation) alongside formats that DANS can archive but cannot guarantee in terms of long-term sustainability and access. These suggested formats are in line with general digital preservation principles (e.g. preference for open, non-proprietary formats, text-based and uncompressed formats, etc.) and reflect those recommended by other digital archives. A taskforce within DANS was started in the summer of 2014 in order to keep the Preferred Formats list up to date; a revision of the document is expected in the Fall of 2014.

In addition to information on how to deposit data, the EASY web pages also provide details on how deposited data is stored, preserved, and accessed. This is covered specifically with the DANS Licence Agreement⁵⁰ - and its accompanying explanatory document⁵¹ - and also more generally within the wider framework of the Data Seal of Approval (see below). DANS also provides a detailed Preservation Policy⁵² document alongside a briefer summary document covering the types of verification and processing that a depositor can expect to have carried out on their deposited data set⁵³.

A number of ‘best practice’ videos have also been made available by DANS on YouTube covering general topics such as data management, data sharing, persistent identifiers and citation⁵⁴.

Data Seal of Approval

The Data Seal of Approval (DSA)⁵⁵ comprises a set of sixteen guidelines / criteria that determine whether a digital archive or repository is capable of ensuring that the data it holds can be discovered, understood and used in the long-term. While initially set up by DANS in 2008, the DSA was handed over to an international board in 2009. As of April 2014, the Data Seal of Approval has been awarded to 27 repositories around the world.

The DSA website provides details of the sixteen guidelines alongside an online tool with which repositories can undertake the self-assessment process required during the application for the Data Seal of Approval. The guidelines themselves, while focussing largely on the responsibilities of the repository regarding the data they hold, also deal with the deposit process (format and metadata

⁴⁹ <http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/EASY/DANS%20preferred%20formats%20UK%20DEF.pdf>

⁵⁰ http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/archief/Licence_agreement_DANS_UK.doc

⁵¹ http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/archief/Explanation_licence_agreement_DANS_UK.doc

⁵² http://dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/EASY/20140220%20Preservation%20Policy%20v1_0.pdf

⁵³ http://www.dans.knaw.nl/sites/default/files/file/Provenance%20document_120823_UK.pdf

⁵⁴ These videos are available through the Research Data Netherlands channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPdYOhL96exPtm_II-BO5og/videos) and the DANS Data Archiving channel (<https://www.youtube.com/user/DANSDataArchiving/videos>)

⁵⁵ <http://www.datasealofapproval.org/en/>

specifications that the depositor should follow) and data dissemination (data licencing and access regulations with regard to data consumers).

As evidenced by its management and community, the DSA is very much an international standard and, as such, fits into a wider framework of Trusted Digital Repository certification alongside other initiatives such as ISO 16363⁵⁶.

DANS itself is currently undertaking a high-level self-evaluation against the criteria specified under the German DIN 31644 standard ('Information und Dokumentation - Kriterien für vertrauenswürdige digitale Langzeitarchive'). The standard, 'Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives', specifies 34 criteria which cover the whole range of activities and responsibilities essential to creating a trustworthy digital archive⁵⁷.

TRiDaS and the DCCD

TRiDaS (Tree Ring Data Standard) is an XML-based international standard for Tree-Ring Data developed as the result of a collaboration between the DANS-hosted DCCD (Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology) repository and the Dendro Data Standard Forum, and funded by the NWO, the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands, and Cornell University in the US. The TRiDaS website⁵⁸ provides the standard's schema⁵⁹ alongside extensive documentation and examples.

The TRiDaS format aims to address the problems and differing implementations of existing and legacy data formats and to provide a common data standard to aid the robust exchange of dendrochronological data and metadata between users and software applications. The process and challenges of creating the standard are discussed in detail in an article published in *Dendrochronologia* Vol.28(2)⁶⁰. In addition to providing the data standard, the TRiDaS website also provides a number of software applications, tools, and libraries to allow developers to incorporate support for reading and writing of the standard into applications.

The TRiDaS standard is also used in the DCCD repository⁶¹, an online digital library of tree-ring data and metadata resulting from various contributed projects. The DCCD repository allows users to contribute, query, and allow access to project dendrochronology datasets (time series, metadata, and associated files e.g. photos and correspondence) within a homogenous environment featuring multi-language vocabularies. The creation and specification for the DCCD repository is discussed in detail in a paper by Jansma et al in *Dendrochronologia* Vol.30(4)⁶².

⁵⁶ <http://www.trusteddigitalrepository.eu/Site/Welcome.html>

⁵⁷ <http://www.nabd.din.de/cmd?artid=147058907&contextid=nabd&subcommitteeid=112656173&bcrumblevel=1&level=tpl-art-detailansicht&committeeid=54738855&languageid=en>

⁵⁸ <http://www.tridas.org/>

⁵⁹ <http://www.tridas.org/download.php>

⁶⁰ Jansma, E., Brewer, P. B. and Zandhuis, I. (2010) 'TRiDaS 1.1: The tree-ring data standard'. *Dendrochronologia* 28(2), 99-130. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2009.06.009>

⁶¹ <http://dendro.dans.knaw.nl/>

⁶² Jansma, E., van Lanen, R. J., Brewer, P. W., Kramer, R. (2012) 'The DCCD: A digital data infrastructure for tree-ring research'. *Dendrochronologia* 30(4), 249-251. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2011.12.002>

2.8 The Discovery Programme (Ireland)

Areas of Expertise

3D documentation, aerial, lidar, and geophysical survey methods.

Relevant Good Practice work

Currently undertaking good practice work on lidar and laser scanning within the 3D-ICONS project and also on aerial and geophysical datasets within the ArchaeoLandscapes project.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Where overlaps exist between ARIADNE and other complimentary projects (i.e. 3D-ICONS and ArchaeoLandscapes) Discovery will aim to coordinate efforts and experts to provide more comprehensive and wider reaching guideline publications e.g.
 - 3D-ICONS - documentation and metadata for 3D datasets (lidar and laser scanning)
 - ArchaeoLandscapes - archiving and documentation of aerial datasets and geophysical survey

Areas where Good Practice work required

Not specified.

The Discovery Programme⁶³, founded in 1991, is an independent public institution set up to undertake research and investigative projects in Ireland. The Discovery Programme is funded by the Heritage Council and led by a Council and Directorate made up of Irish archaeologists from across the sector (e.g. museums, universities, government departments, private sector). The governing bodies identify areas of research which are then pursued as individual Discovery Programme projects, the results of which are then communicated back to the community via a variety of methods (publications, lectures, community events, etc.). In addition to undertaking and communicating research, the Discovery Programme also promotes the use of new technologies in Irish archaeology.

Discovery Programme provided information on the following areas of expertise and good practice:

At present the Discovery Programme utilises the current ADS Guides to Good Practice⁶⁴ as a matter of course. Currently there are no equivalent documents in Ireland but an assessment is underway of the suitability of guidelines produced by the Digital repository of Ireland (DRI)⁶⁵. The Discovery Programme is also currently involved (alongside other ARIADNE partners) in two European projects. Both projects aim to publish their output by the end of 2014.

3D-ICONS

Under the 3D-ICONS project⁶⁶, the Discovery Programme is contributing to the production of guidelines on the 3D documentation (including metadata) of archaeology through techniques such as lidar and terrestrial laser scanning. The guidelines aim to cover the whole range of the pipeline/workflow including data capture, modelling, metadata and paradata, archiving and IPR.

ArchaeoLandscapes

As a partner in the EU Culture funded ArchaeoLandscapes project⁶⁷, the Discovery Programme is producing procedural guidelines focussed largely on data acquisition, processing, and archiving for geophysical survey, aerial archives and lidar. These guidelines will be published in the form of PDF documents and eBooks.

⁶³ <http://www.discoveryprogramme.ie/>

⁶⁴ <http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk>

⁶⁵ <http://www.dri.ie/>

⁶⁶ <http://3dicons-project.eu/>

⁶⁷ <http://www.archaeolandscapes.eu/>

2.9 Inrap (France)

Areas of Expertise

Excavation and fieldwork data.

Relevant Good Practice work

Management and dissemination of scientific and field data.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

Case studies applying existing guides to Inrap datasets.

Areas where Good Practice work required

None specified.

The French National Institute for Preventive Archaeological Research (Inrap)⁶⁸ was created in 2002 to ensure the recording and study of archaeological heritage affected by development and infrastructure work. Inrap is a public research institution under the supervision of the Ministry of Culture and Communication and the Ministry on Research and Higher Education. Within these Ministries, Inrap's functions include archaeological fieldwork, scientific studies, contributions to education, and the dissemination and enhancement of archaeological research to both the general public and scientific communities. Inrap itself is organised into eight regional headquarters with fifty archaeological centres.

Inrap's Scientific and Technical Directorate (DST) is specifically involved in identifying methods and techniques and making methodological recommendations as part of national harmonisation. DST also has a role in organising knowledge from archaeological work and how this is distributed to the archaeological community. Beyond this, DST also defines areas of research, scientific publications, policy cooperation with other research organisations, and looks to inform the evolution of scientific and technical skills and needs in terms of training and scientific assessment.

Inrap has provided the following information on areas of expertise and good practice:

Although Inrap currently has no good practice guidelines for digital data, it does follow a metadata schema for the recording of archaeological excavation reports (based on the UNIMARC standard). Inrap has also recently been working in collaboration with CINES, (the National Computer Centre for Higher Education) to archive PDF excavation reports and have adopted their metadata schema (based on Dublin Core). The schema covers the key Dublin Core descriptive elements together by incorporating a number of 'management' elements and file metadata (i.e. file name, format, and checksum).

DOLIA

DOLIA⁶⁹ is an online system used by Inrap to manage and disseminate scientific documentation. The system, based on the Ever Team content management system 'Flora', was set up for Inrap between 2008 and 2009. DOLIA employs international library standards, specifically the UNIMARC format. Resources within DOLIA are described using the PACTOLS thesauri⁷⁰ produced by the archaeological network FRANTIQU (Fédération et ressources sur l'Antiquité)⁷¹ supported by the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS). PACTOLS includes six thesauri focussed on antiquity and archaeology from prehistory to the industrial age, and are poly-hierarchical, scalable and multilingual.

⁶⁸ <http://www.inrap.fr/>

⁶⁹ <http://dolia.inrap.fr/inrapgestdoc/jsp/index.jsp?lang=en>

⁷⁰ <http://frantiq.mom.fr/thesaurus-pactols>

⁷¹ <http://frantiq.mom.fr/>

2.10 MiBACT-ICCU (Italy)

Areas of Expertise

Documentation and cataloguing of archaeological assets including artefacts, monuments, and archaeological stratigraphy from excavation.

Relevant Good Practice work

Authority files, terminological tools, standards for the description and production of accessory documentation, standards for the documentation of archaeological assets.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Good practices for data encoding of archaeological information concerning finds, monuments and archaeological sites
- Archaeological thesauri and vocabularies
- Guides for long term preservation of digital cultural heritage

Areas where Good Practice work required

- Guidelines for IPR and data access
- Scientific archaeological documentation: models on relief / recovery architectures and archaeological objects
- Standards for cartographic representation (2D/3D) of territorial archaeological data, with regard on integration with cartographic models (e.g. GeoUML)
- Standardisation of WebGIS applications
- Research, testing and dissemination of digital identities for federated access to cultural resources, scientific databases.

ICCU, the Central Institute for the Union Catalogue of the Italian libraries, is an institute of the Italian Ministry for Cultural Heritage and Activities (MiBACT), the State Ministry in charge of cultural heritage documentation, management, and protection. ICCU is responsible for the coordination of ministerial digitisation activities and, specifically, for two portal initiatives related to e-infrastructures for digital cultural heritage; Internet Culturale⁷² and Culturaitalia⁷³. These portals jointly serve up nearly twelve million records from Italian libraries and cultural institutions, providing access to a range of publications and digital resources.

MiBACT-ICCU has provided information on the following institutions and related areas of expertise and good practice.

The Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation (ICCD) of the Italian Ministry for Culture and Tourism.

Activity within the ICCD⁷⁴ focuses on the research and development of tools, methods and standards for knowledge, protection, and the enhancement of Italian cultural and artistic heritage. Among these activities, a significant task is the management of the National General Catalogue of archaeological, architectural, historical, artistic and ethno-anthropological heritage alongside the development of cataloguing methodologies and standards and the coordination of technical institutions involved.

In this context, the ICCD provides standards, methodologies and guides for the technological management of the general catalogue. Cataloguing procedures are monitored and assessed through

⁷² <http://www.internetculturale.it/opencms/opencms/it/>

⁷³ <http://www.culturaitalia.it/>

⁷⁴ <http://memoriafuturo.fondazionerosselli.org/en/enti/central-institute-for-cataloguing-and-documentation-iccd/> (outline in English)

the ICCD Observatory for Cataloguing, an internal committee in charge of the various management institutions and activities related to cataloguing activities, and also through the topics, best practices and experiences related in the guidelines of the regional Compendium for cataloguing.

Tools for data management include the SIGECweb⁷⁵ (Information System General Catalogue), a web-based application created to unify and streamline processes related to cultural heritage cataloguing activities and to ensure the quality of the data produced and their compliance with national standards. The system controls the entire flow of the cataloguing process in a single homogeneous environment, managing all process flows and allowing, in real time, the propagation of standards, functional upgrades, and their availability for sharing with other systems. SIGECweb has an integrated GIS⁷⁶ that allows the management of geographic information related to cultural heritage within the system. The data are visible only to authorised users.

The ICCD corpus of cataloguing standards consists of regulations, support and control tools (e.g. vocabularies, lists of terms) and a set of rules and guidelines illustrating the methods to be followed for the acquisition and production of cultural heritage documentation. In particular the corpus includes:

- Regulations for cataloguing, describing the data models and the Authority files to be used for cataloguing activities. Each regulation contains the data structure schema of the related data model and the rules for compilation, providing details on how individual fields should be filled in.
- Catalogue schemas: descriptive models and forms for collecting information in a structured way, according to a ‘path of knowledge’ that guides the users and, at the same time, controls the acquisition and encoding of data according to specific criteria. The ICCD issued different cataloguing schemas in relation to different types of assets, organised on the basis of the various disciplines (see below).
- Authority files, a complete control system to guarantee uniformity in the use of information concerning key concepts (e.g. authors, bibliography references) used throughout the whole system. The Authority files are useful support tools for the standardisation of cataloguing, and come as self-contained databases to be connected with the cultural heritage ones. ICCD created and maintain three Authority files for archaeology:
 - “AUT” (Authors)
 - “DSC” (Archaeological Excavations)
 - “RCG” (Archaeological Surveys)
- Support and control tools: thesauri and terminological tools developed to perform data acquisition in a uniform way by using similar criteria, and to create a “common and shared language”, essential for a correct use of information at query time and for the interoperability of cultural heritage data. Each regulation provides support and control tools to populate specific fields. Essentially, these are vocabularies that are either ‘closed’ (default list of terms that can be increased with other entries only by an activity carried out by the ICCD) or ‘open’ (list which may also be increased with terms proposed by cataloguers and included in the standard terminology after a scientific audit by ICCD).

A number of standards documents are available online⁷⁷ covering the acquisition (resolution, formats, general quality issues, etc.) of digital images and multimedia files.

⁷⁵ <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/index.php?it/118/sistema-informativo-generale-del-catalogo-sigec>

⁷⁶ <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/index.php?it/393/modulo-cartografico>

⁷⁷ <http://www.iccd.beniculturali.it/index.php?it/115/standard-catalografici>

Culturaitalia, the Italian National Aggregator

Culturaitalia⁷⁸ is the Portal of Italian Culture, promoted by MiBACT, and involving cultural institutions from all sectors and levels (national, regional and local). Culturaitalia plays an important role in the development of Europeana by making available cooperative networks and agreements and coordinating technical activities. Culturaitalia promotes the interoperability of digital resources through the adoption of a cross-domain application profile (PICO AP) based on the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative technical guidelines. While the PICO AP supports various encoding schemes (i.e. international standards and thesauri or ontologies), a specific thesaurus has been defined in order to describe the Italian cultural domain and to give a hierarchical order to the resources available in the index of Culturaitalia.

The PICO Thesaurus is organised into four main categories: Who, What, Where, When:

- “Who” includes both people and corporate bodies
- “What” covers both tangible and intangible heritage and all digital objects
- “Where” covers Italian places (from regions to towns and villages)
- “When” includes a list of chronological (period) keywords associated to a predefined range of years.

The Thesaurus is bilingual with versions in both Italian and English in SKOS format. Technical documentation is also available online⁷⁹.

There is also a section of Culturaitalia devoted to Open Data: The pilot project⁸⁰ contains open data sets from Culturaitalia released by the project partners under a “CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication” licence. The data is searchable:

- Through a SPARQL endpoint that provides access to RDF metadata structured according to the CIDOC - Conceptual Reference Model in the implementation of Erlangen CRM / OWL. Data can be searched over three querying interfaces and are linked to authority files such as VIAF (Virtual International Authority File [<http://www.viaf.org>]); GeoNames [<http://www.geonames.org/>]; PICO Thesaurus in SKOS, DCMI Type vocabulary.
- OAI Provider that makes available XML or RDF metadata structured according to different schemas:
 - oai-dc (xml): OAI-PMH schema adopted by Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
 - pico (xml): PICO Application Profile, the Culturaitalia Application Profile
 - edm (rdf): Europeana Data Model, adopted by the portal Europeana
 - cidoc (rdf): CIDOC - Conceptual Reference Model in the implementation of Erlangen CRM / OWL

SITAR

SITAR⁸¹ is the Archaeological Territorial Informative System of Rome and was launched in 2007 by the Soprintendenza Speciale per i Beni Archeologici di Roma (SSBAR). The system manages diverse data

⁷⁸ <http://www.culturaitalia.it>

⁷⁹ http://www.culturaitalia.it/opencms/documentazione_tecnica_en.jsp?language=en&tematica=static

⁸⁰ <http://dati.culturaitalia.it>

⁸¹ Technical documentation:

http://archeoroma.beniculturali.it/sites/default/files/Il%20Progetto%20SITAR%20della%20Soprintendenza%20Speciale%20per%20i%20Beni%20Archeologici%20di%20Roma_0.pdf

sets ranging from large monumental contexts to single archaeological features found in rescue excavations or planned investigations and carried out in the territory of the Cities of Rome and Fiumicino. SITAR currently manages more than 10,000 digital objects.

In terms of Good Practice, the project follows the guidelines of INSPIRE, the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community, set by the European Parliament and European Council (Dir. 2007/2/CEE of 14 March 2007).

The overall goal of the SITAR project is to publish recorded and interpreted data using Web Feature Service (WFS) and Web Map Service (WMS) standards and technologies in order to share both descriptive and spatial databases with other offices involved with town planning. The system also records all scientific data derived from investigations (both rescue and planned) carried out in the territory of the Soprintendenza.

As an Information System, SITAR brings together various types of data sets, ranging from large monumental contexts to single archaeological features found in rescue excavations in the territory of Rome. The logic of SITAR is based on 4 primary information layers (and a fifth currently still in development):

- **ORIGINI DELL'INFORMAZIONE:** the source of information i.e. administrative and scientific information from the archaeological excavation or geophysical/geological survey
- **PARTIZIONI ARCHEOLOGICHE:** the scientific description of archaeological findings even if fragmentary, following the chronological or functional criteria
- **UNITÀ ARCHEOLOGICHE :** derived by the logical union of more 'partizioni archeologiche' which together makes an archaeological complex (for example a specific building)
- **DISPOSITIVI DI VINCOLO :** the law-constraints which punctually preserves the important monuments but not their contexts;
- **POTENZIALE ARCHEOLOGICO** (the "archaeological potential"): it is generated by the logic union and super-interpretation of the base layers. Local authorities and institutional bodies must bear the 'potenziale archeologico' map in mind when working on the urban development of a territory

In the SITAR information architecture the four primary levels correspond to well-structured archives that include all corresponding spatial data shown in the map of the various features classes.

Other Guidelines

In addition to those mentioned above, various other practice documents and guidelines for Italian archaeology and cultural heritage exist. These include general Italian guidelines for the practice of preventive archaeology⁸² together with European-wide guidelines, such as the UNESCO Convention on the Protection of the Underwater Cultural Heritage⁸³, employed by MiBACT-ICCU and covering general elements such as project design, reporting, and the composition and deposition of archives.

ICCU has also been involved in the Athena project (2008-2011), which produced a number of booklets⁸⁴ focussed on best practice and standards in digitisation, geographic information, and persistent identifiers. Additionally, ICCU is currently involved in the Digital Cultural Heritage Roadmap for Preservation⁸⁵ (DCH-RP) project, which looks at best practice for preservation

⁸² <http://www.archeologia.beniculturali.it/index.php?it/222/documenti-e-linee-guida/4/linee-guida-per-larcheologia-preventiva-la-circolare-n-102012>

⁸³ http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=13520&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html

⁸⁴ <http://www.athenaeurope.org/>

⁸⁵ <http://www.dch-rp.eu>

standards. The DCH-RP project will present the final version of its Roadmap on 22nd September 2014 in Rome, at the project's final conference.

While not directly involving ICCU, the MAPPA project⁸⁶ is the first open-data archaeological project in Italy, and thus potentially present a successful example of the open storage and dissemination of archaeological data within an Italian context. In 2013, during the conference organised by MAPPA, ADS and DANS provided knowledge regarding good practice for the long term preservation of archaeological data, open access policies, and shared experiences of setting up national online repositories as an example.

⁸⁶ http://mappaproject.arch.unipi.it/?page_id=136&lang=en

2.11 MNM-NÖK (Hungary)

Areas of Expertise

Documentation and storage of datasets from excavation, fieldwork and survey.

Relevant Good Practice work

Two published guidelines (Hungarian language only) focussed on recording and storing excavation and fieldwork datasets. Internal guides and protocols for various data types e.g. GPS.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

- Contribution and possible case study looking at archiving Hungarian geophysical survey data.
- Application and development of project-level metadata.
- Contribution to guidelines on storing and preserving GPS survey datasets.

Areas where Good Practice work required

Archiving geophysical survey data and creation of project-level metadata.

The National Heritage Centre of the Hungarian National Museum was established in 2007 and, as a result, all archaeological data is held digitally. The Centre is responsible for archaeological excavation and recording, monument protection, a range of scientific analyses, artefact processing, preservation, and restoration.

MNM-NÖK has provided the following information on best practices and procedures associated with the creation, recording, and storage of excavation datasets:

Excavation datasets

Excavation documentation held by MNM-NÖK is comprised of a range of files covering both archaeological assessment and excavation (e.g. impact study / shovel test of sites, extended excavation reports, feature and site maps and descriptions, photos and photo inventories, GPS coordinates, feature drawings, restoration documentation, scientific reports). Excavation datasets are digitised in a standardised format in terms of document structure and chapters. All associated digital files (documents, pictures, drawings, CAD files etc.) are also named in a standardised way (e.g. filenames include elements which show the project type, type of document, etc.) allowing files for a particular excavation to be easily collated within a database.

Two guidelines have recently been made available online (in Hungarian). A first guide (2013) looks generally at excavation and the required documentation⁸⁷. The second guide (2014) focuses in more detail on Archaeological Assessment⁸⁸ and includes documentation guidelines covering field survey, geophysical survey and aerial archaeology. Section 7.2 of this guide specifically looks at what digital files should be included in site documentation, structural elements to be included within these, recommendations for file formats for each type, and outlines a file naming and folder structure.

After the submission of a dataset, the Department of Archaeological Processing copies all files to a secure server - essentially a restricted access archive - where no accidental change is possible. All files are therefore kept on a central server but individual archaeologists may also keep a copy of the

⁸⁷ <http://www.MNM-NOK.gov.hu/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/d-Egyseges-felt%C3%A1r%C3%A1si-%C3%A9s-dokument%C3%A1ci%C3%B3s-rendszer.pdf>

⁸⁸ <http://www.MNM-NOK.gov.hu/wp-content/uploads/2013/01/b-ERD-szakmai-%C3%BAtmutat%C3%B3.pdf>

dataset on their own computer. The archived datasets on the central server are additionally backed up every day to a different server.

Apart from being stored in a digital format, excavation datasets are also placed in the archive of the MNM-NÖK in paper format and on CD/DVD (commercial format). Moreover, according to law, further paper and digital copies (CD/DVD) are also sent to various other associated institutions such as the Archive of the Hungarian National Museum, the relevant County Museum, the Lajos Lechner Innovation and Knowledge Centre, the District Office of Construction and Heritage Protection, as well as to the investor.

Where specific excavations or techniques produce uncommon file formats (e.g. GIS, 3D, micro-Pixe etc.), these files are included within the archived dataset. Software support for these files is not provided but information regarding which free software can be used is made available. Examples include magnetometry data archived as both raster files together with the original surfer files (.SRF). This approach is viewed as necessary in order to preserve access to the additional data stored in the original file that may not be retained or accessible in the exported raster file.

Geophysical Survey

Geophysical surveys recently became an integrated part of archaeological assessments resulting in an increase in surveying (150+ hectares in 2013). This marks the beginning of such surveys in Hungary on such a scale and presents a need to focus on creating an archiving strategy in order to avoid later problems. As mentioned above, the present approach relies on storing the original Surfer files alongside raster data. Simple storage of just the raster dataset (e.g. in TIFF or JPG formats) could result in loss of information as the original point data is lost and no additional gridding or filtering is possible. A problem however exists in that Surfer is a commercial software package and therefore not available to everyone. An additional approach is the archiving of original TXT or DAT files instead so that the original point cloud data is not lost.

Field Survey Data / GPS datasets

MNM-NÖK also routinely collect and archive field survey data from hand-held GPS systems. These largely result from field walking surveys and consist of tracklogs and point data as GPX files. Often these more detailed datasets are lost in the documentation while a survey polygon of the assumed extent of the site is often archived. MNM-NÖK have a protocol / best practice for documenting and for conducting such field surveys (e.g. how close the swaths should be, how to collect pottery etc.).

2.12 NIAM-BAS (Bulgaria)

Areas of Expertise

Field survey and excavation.

Relevant Good Practice work

AIS AKB development.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

Storage of GPS data within AKB.

Areas where Good Practice work required

None specified.

The National Institute of Archaeology and Museum at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NIAM-BAS) is the national centre and coordinator for field research in Bulgaria. The Institute was established in 1949 as successor to the Department of Valuables and the Bulgarian Institute of Archaeology, which was the first academic institute in Bulgaria.

NIAM-BAS consists of a number of structural units including five chronological and subject departments, a Department for Interdisciplinary Research, two Branches for excavations at the Old Bulgarian capitals (Shumen and Veliko Tarnovo) and a Museum of Archaeology. The Institute undertakes various types of fieldwork including regular, rescue and emergency archaeological excavations.

Various activities of NIAM-BAS are performed in close collaboration and interaction with the museums in the country as well as state institutions (Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Education and Science, National Institute of Cultural Monuments), regional and local executive authorities, and various nongovernmental organisations. NIAM-BAS also collaborates on various projects supported by national and international funds.

NIAM-BAS has provided information on the AIS AKB National Database as an example of good practice.

AIS AKB

The Automated Information System Archaeological Map of Bulgaria (AIS AKB) is a national Database for archaeological sites. AIS AKB was created in 1990 in order to fulfil a social function for the management of archaeological resources, their preservation, and to aid scientific investigations. The first version was completed in 1992 and was designed to work under the DOS operating system. In 2000 a new version of the database was created which allowed its use under Windows. The AIS AKB was subsequently upgraded in 2010 to an online system. AIS AKB is protected by an issue of the Bulgarian Ministry of Culture released in 2011 that strictly defines its structure, support and restricted access.

Since 1992 more than 17,000 sites have been registered in the database by Bulgarian archaeologists employed by national institutions, universities, and from regional and local museums.

The online system is supported by – and developed from – a set of guidance publications titled ‘Guides for entering registration cards in AIS AKB’, first developed in 1992. These guidelines are available in electronic format to Bulgarian archaeologists but they are not publicly published. They contain guidelines for conducting archaeological surface surveys, thesauri for archaeological site types, structures, and finds; chronological and cultural terms; soil, hydrographic, and orographic types; administrative divisions, and the condition of the archaeological site.

Structure of the AIS AKB

The structure of the AIS AKB consists of a hierarchy of data elements under a main ‘Archaeological Object’ (AO) element. Aside from basic descriptive, temporal and spatial elements, the AIS AKB system records a range of information on associated finds, geology, land use and terrain, ownership and chronology.

The AIS AKB Archaeological Objects function as brief ‘reports’ for archaeological work. The AOs themselves may vary from complex dig sites to individual features or rarely even individual finds. For example, a single entry may exist for a settlement or single tomb or separate entries may exist for an entire settlement and important objects within. The different policies in different periods of the existence of the system and its predecessors reflect the granularity of the reports – there are periods when separate entries have been created for important features / layers / finds in a single dig site and there are periods when the entries were more general – covering an entire site and including multiple cultural layers or finds. There is an on-going effort to introduce some linking between the entries and thus create more detailed descriptions and relations where possible, but it is still in an early stage and data connections will need some time to amount in order to become useful.

The current system also allows associated plans, maps, photos, and documents to be stored along with basic descriptive metadata. Older AOs from previous versions have been enriched with scanned images but the bulk of entries from previous versions do not include electronic representations of the maps and plots, photos and documents.

The meaning of most data types within the system is obvious, but some of the nomenclatures have deep structure and can further be used for the extraction of data of different types. For example, the ‘Classification’ elements can consist of the two attributes ‘Type’ and ‘Chronology’, both of which use extensive controlled vocabulary lists. The classification of features and finds also employs an extensive controlled vocabulary.

There is currently no field to enable the user to specify the possible date (year / century) of a find or feature. All the information is collected in the classification mentioned above. The available data shows that this had a positive effect in the long run – the time period classification is not very precise, but the tolerance stimulated the users to specify the chronology more responsibly which led to very few wrong time period classifications. It may be best to evolve this to a dual option enabling the user to specify a time period as year/ century and time period as classification nomenclature as possible at the time of data entry.

2.13 OEAW (Austria)

Areas of Expertise

Archaeological excavation (site and finds data)

Relevant Good Practice work

Resource metadata schema work

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

Case studies, specifically looking at metadata schemas and file formats

Areas where Good Practice work required

Resource metadata

The Austrian Academy of Sciences (Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, OEAW), founded in 1847, is the national body for science and research in Austria. Consisting of 28 institutions, OEAW conducts national and international research over a wide range of disciplines. Within OEAW, OREA (the Institute for Oriental and European Archaeology) conducts research over a wide range of areas including archaeological fieldwork and material studies, together with interdisciplinary work in areas such as archaeozoology and botany, anthropology, paleogenetics, geoarchaeology and landscape modelling.

OEAW has provided information on the following areas of expertise and good practice:

Currently there are no common guidelines regarding digital archiving, documentation or data acquisition at the Austrian Academy of Sciences. Researchers are advised to follow common scientific and academic guidelines and keep (primary) data for at least 10 years after creation. How this data should be organised and archived is not specified.

Each discipline within OEAW has developed its own research practice but the various types of data (e.g. text, images, literature/references, CAD, GIS, etc.) are normally structured and stored within a folder system and additional databases. 'Good Practice' therefore largely depends on a personal approach with researchers free to organise their data as they see fit. While this provides, at the very least, a certain level of organisation, it has been noted internally that this results in a corresponding lack of structured metadata and additional documentation.

Archaeological Surveying

There currently exist generic documentation system guidelines, released in 2012 by the Austrian Federal Monuments Office responsible for Cultural Heritage (Bundesdenkmalamt, Abteilung für Archäologie)⁸⁹. These guidelines cover data creation and documentation requirements for excavation data and include reporting requirements for a range of archaeological fieldwork techniques. The guide also covers elements such as finds documentation and the structure of archaeological reports. Digital datasets are covered briefly in that, for example, requirements for plans include file format recommendations (e.g. CAD files as DWG or DXF) and photogrammetric recording and photo specifications include file formats (i.e. JPG, RAW and TIFF) and some basic metadata. Section 7 of the guide provides a general summary of file formats for a range of data types. The guide also suggests some basic back up advice for digital data.

Resource-level Metadata

Recent work by OREA has focussed on the development of a provisional metadata schema for the OREA data inventory, aiming to provide an overview of digital and non-digital resources held at

⁸⁹ <http://www.bundesdenkmalamt.at/documents/621701608.pdf>

OREA. The schema, incorporating project-, resource- and file-level metadata, is intended to identify data management and archiving needs as well as feed into the development of new projects for the new OEAW Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (ACDH). The project, which has incorporated a survey of archaeologists, is currently in the reporting stage and is looking to develop the schema within the next two years.

2.14 ZRC-SAZU (Slovenia)

Areas of Expertise

Archaeological site recording, aerial survey and lidar, 3D datasets and dissemination of 3D data.

Relevant Good Practice work

ARKAS data standard, aerial and lidar guide development under ArchaeoLandscapes project.

Proposed areas of contribution for Guides to Good Practice (T4.6/D4.6)

Monitoring and coordination between the ArchaeoLandscapes project and ARIADNE, particularly in reference to:

- lidar guidance. ZRC SAZU are preparing a Guide on 'Lidar data visualization techniques' - the final product can be both the product of ArchaeoLandscapes and Ariadne
- specific elements that may be used to supplement the existing ADS aerial survey guide.
- ArchaeoLandscapes case studies that illustrate the application of the guides.

Areas where Good Practice work required

Recording digital files and datasets (i.e. development of the e-archive system). Recording of oral and folk traditions (i.e. Database of Tradition and Space).

ZRC-SAZU, the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Arts and Sciences, is a national centre consisting of eighteen individual research institutes, including the Institute of Archaeology and the Institute of Anthropological and Spatial Studies. The Centre undertakes interdisciplinary research as part of national programmes and research projects, international projects, and as part of centres of excellence. The Centre is supported by a research infrastructure that includes museums, laboratory services, and a publishing house.

Generally, ZRC-SAZU encompasses a wide range of areas of expertise through its teams of researchers and technical and specialist advisors. More specifically, alongside traditional reference collections, ZRC-SAZU holds and maintains a number of databases and digital collections, some of which are available online. These collections cover a range of subjects from the national monuments and photograph databases (e.g. ARKAS⁹⁰) and regional site databases (e.g. Zbiva⁹¹) down to site-specific (e.g. Ptuj) or collection-specific (Roman coarse pottery, archaeozoology, palynological) databases.

ZRC-SAZU has provided information on the following projects illustrating areas of best practice and expertise:

- ARKAS
- databases
- e-archive
- ArchaeoLandscapes

⁹⁰ <http://arkas.zrc-sazu.si/>

⁹¹ <http://zrcalo1.zrc-sazu.si/zbiva/>

ARKAS

ARKAS is the online database of archaeological sites (immovable heritage) in Slovenia, and incorporates a data standard for the creation and recording of archaeological data. The ARKAS archaeological data standardisation guidelines⁹² were created in 2004 (updated in 2008) to address the situation in Slovenia where archaeological data was being recorded by various organisations at a number of different levels (e.g. index level metadata all the way down to detailed survey or object level information). The database itself aims to record four main areas of information: the site (location, site type, period), related field research and protection, sources of information, and related finds and archives held by the Institute of Archaeology.

The standard itself has been developed out of existing Slovenian standards and through comparisons with other European standards such as those used by the Danish National Record of Cultural History (DKC) and the UK MIDAS standard. In addition, ARKAS has also been developed through comparisons with the CIDOC data standard.

Databases

In addition to the ARKAS database, ZRC-SAZU also host a number of on-line and offline databases covering a wide range of subjects. These are described below:

- Libera⁹³ - a database of archaeological literature relating to Central Europe in 5-11th centuries held by the library of the Institute of Archaeology. (Online)
- Zbiva⁹⁴ - a sites database for the East Alps in the early Middle Ages covering sites, graves and objects. (Online).
- Ptuj - a database specific to the Roman town of Poetovio. The database has the same structure as ARKAS. (Offline but partially published in the form of an e-book⁹⁵)
- Digital archive of the Institute of Archaeology - an internal institute database of archaeological, epigraphical, archaeozoological, palynological and archaeobotanical material held by the Institute of Archaeology. (Offline)
- Roman Course Pottery Database⁹⁶ - The roman coarse pottery database enables the systematic processing of ceramic material within a unified database and includes the objective and unified descriptions of forms and fabrics alongside drawings and photos of the vessels. (Online)
- Digital Images of Inscriptions from Slovenia - a database incorporating site data with selected bibliography and images of epigraphical monuments from Slovenia. (Offline)
- Zooarchaeological Collections - a comparative osteological collection of mammal bones. (Offline)
- Palynological collection - a pollen reference collection. (Offline)
- Archaeobotanical Collection - reference collection. (Offline)
- Database of Tradition and Space – an online database for the spatial recording of oral and folk traditions. Slovenian only. (Online)

⁹² <http://arkas.zrc-sazu.si/index.php?kaj=standardization.main>

⁹³ http://zrcalo1.zrc-sazu.si/libera/lang_en/predstavitev.htm

⁹⁴ <http://zrcalo1.zrc-sazu.si/zbiva/frameset.php?lang=en>

⁹⁵ <http://iza2.zrc-sazu.si/sites/default/files/9789612542375.pdf>

⁹⁶ http://groba-keramika.zrc-sazu.si/groba_ker.html

e-archive Slovenia

The Slovenian 'e-archive' database is a system, developed up to 2009, for internally recording files sent to the archive. The database sits alongside a complementary file structure (structured directory system), which stores the actual datasets. The system was briefly used during its pilot phase and currently contains five site datasets.

ArchaeoLandscapes

ZRC-SAZU is also involved in the ArchaeoLandscapes project and is providing expertise for the creation and documentation of aerial and lidar dataset guidance documents alongside a number of other ARIADNE partners. Specifically, ZRC-SAZU is leading the WP8 – technical guidance and advice on best practice in aerial survey, remote sensing and landscape studies and preparing guides on 'Lidar data visualization techniques'.

Other areas of expertise include general 3D datasets, the dissemination of 3D data, and a specialisation in Central European archaeology.

3 Assessment of Practice and Areas of Expertise

This section assesses the major themes in terms of practice and areas of expertise reported in the previous section. In turn, the themes discussed below provide the background for the contributions to the Guides to Good Practice (Task 4.6) outlined in the subsequent section

While this report inevitably touches on standards and metadata, these elements are reported in more detail along with information on data holdings (file formats and data types) in ARIADNE D3.2 *Report on Project Standards* and in D3.3 *Report on Data Sharing Policies*.

3.1 Digital Archives and Repositories

While all the partner organisations collect and store digital data at a variety of levels, three of the ARIADNE partners – ADS, DAI, and DANS – actively research, publish, and promote guidelines and best practice documents for the digital preservation of a wide range of archaeological datasets. CYI-STARC can also be included in this group through their digital repository development work although this is specifically focussed on 3D datasets, file formats for their dissemination, and metadata.

The general focus of these organisations in terms of expertise is on ingest, storage, preservation, and dissemination of archaeological data and incorporates consideration of file formats for preservation and dissemination, and metadata specifications.

A number of previous projects such as ACE⁹⁷ (ADS and DANS) and CARARE⁹⁸ (ADS, DANS and CYI-STARC), alongside a history of close collaboration, have resulted in a level of cooperation between these organisations in the development of guidelines. As a result of this background, together with general well-established theory and approaches in the larger field of digital preservation, the guidelines and good practices created by each of these organisations share a common approach and implementation. In a large number of examples this has resulted in almost identical procedures for certain data types.

In terms of where these larger sets of guidelines can be developed under the ARIADNE project, a key opportunity lies in the synchronisation and referencing between sets of guidelines, specifically where certain areas are better developed in one partner's guidelines. The specific focus of CYI-STARC on 3D data offers a clear area of expertise for other repositories and archives involved in the ARIADNE project. The multilingual nature of the guidelines held by ADS, DAI, and DANS, also presents a possibility of translating existing guidelines, again to cover potential gaps, but also to provide a richer set of guidelines to other partner organisations in their native language (e.g. OEAW would also benefit from more German language guidelines).

3.2 National Databases

Most, if not all, ARIADNE partners involved in Task 4.4 are involved at some level with the hosting, maintenance, or population of some form of national archaeological or cultural heritage database. As would be expected from such a diverse range of organisations, these databases vary in both scale and content from national fieldwork and museum databases such as those at Inrap, MiBACT-ICCU and NIAM-BAS down to smaller regional or type-specific databases and repositories such as those hosted by CYI-STARC, ARUP-CAS, and ZRC-SAZU.

⁹⁷ <http://www.ace-archaeology.eu/>

⁹⁸ <http://www.carare.eu/>

While not guidelines themselves, these large databases exist as structured systems for storing data and implicitly promote a way of recording information (what is recorded and how it is recorded) that is often additionally supported by more formal documentation or user manuals (e.g. the ARKAS system in Slovenia or AIS AKB in Bulgaria). While some of these systems have been developed organically in isolation, often over long periods of time, and reflect the development and responsibilities of their host organisation, others have been developed to additionally tie in to broader international standards and guidelines (e.g. the Romanian DOCPAT system and CIDOC). While, as a result of such development, these systems are often specific to the needs and responsibilities of their host organisation or country, the choices made when designing such systems together with the range of functionality and experience of using and maintaining them, are undoubtedly of benefit to partners looking to create or expand systems of their own.

An additional area of expertise focuses on how these databases are used both in terms of functionality and access. Some of the database systems described here (e.g. Inrap's DOLIA system and the ACERA system reported by ARHEO) move beyond the simple recording of archaeological work as a 'database record' to include associated documents and files (e.g. images or GIS) within the system, essentially moving towards a digital repository. While the long-term preservation element – one, if not *the* primary concern of a digital archive - is often missing from these systems, continued access to these associated files is obviously a key concern and an area where expertise in terms of file storage and formats may be usefully shared.

While not full excavation datasets (discussed below), these large databases with associated files represent the most common set of data held by all partners. While the structure and function of the database is largely tailored to individual needs, the associated files (e.g. reports or images) accompanying database records are often stored in formats that are not best suited to long-term preservation and access. Such datasets present a broad test bed - ideal as the basis for case studies - in terms of best practice for documentation, metadata and data structure requirements.

3.3 Excavation and Field Survey Data

As discussed above, while excavation datasets and data from field surveys can often be a key component of national databases, full datasets resulting from fieldwork and measured surveys are stored by a number of organisations separately to any centralised record or report.

As would be expected, all partner organisations deal with, and have expertise in either creating or storing excavation and field survey datasets at some level. For some organisations, such as a national body like Inrap or research institutes such as ARHEO, there is a 'closed loop' relationship between those who create the data and those who store the resulting datasets. In such situations there is little to no conflict between the types of data being created and the ability of that organisation to store it, the result being that best practice documents and guidelines are highly specific to the work undertaken by the organisation. Other organisations, such as ADS or DANS, who do not undertake fieldwork and whose remit is the archiving and dissemination of data created by a range of researchers and fieldworker, necessarily have a broader range of guidelines which aim to cover most possibilities.

Documents, specifically digital reports, plans, drawings, data-tables, photographs, and spatial data (GIS or GPS/survey data) appear to be the most common type of data stored by all partner organisations and, as mentioned previously, these datasets may be stored in a digital archive or repository system or as a component of a larger database or registry of archaeological sites and fieldwork. Guidance on how this data is stored varies extensively between partners. Some partners have guidelines on how the dataset should be structured (e.g. ARUP-CAS) and others extend this to include preferred file formats and metadata requirements for files and data types (e.g. MNM-NÖK and OEAW).

Such variation highlights an issue in that, while almost all partner organisations deal at some level with basic excavation and field survey datasets, there is varying awareness or concern for the documentation and long term preservation (i.e. accessibility) of these files. This is reflected by the request of at least half of the partner organisations to further develop top-level guidelines and practice focussed on the management of digital resources i.e. resource- and project-level metadata together with the recording/documenting of digital files and datasets.

3.4 Geophysical Survey Data

In addition to those excavation datasets created and stored by the majority of partner organisations, geophysical survey data has been highlighted as both an area of expertise for some partners and one that, for others, requires the development of more guidance. As with excavation datasets, ARIADNE partner organisations are involved with geophysical data at a variety of levels from the creation of geophysical datasets through to the archiving and storage.

ADS has undertaken specific work on producing guidelines for the archiving and documentation of geophysical survey data while DAI, Discovery Programme, and ZRC-SAZU are currently involved, via the ArchaeoLandscapes project, in the development of additional guidance material. A number of other partners, such as ARHEO, ARUP-CAS, and MNM-NÖK are also looking to share individual expertise and improve methods.

As highlighted by the MNM-NÖK report (above, Section 2.11), geophysical survey data is one of the more technical and problematic datasets produced by archaeologists, often involving a variety of techniques and producing a range of data types. Highlighted specifically in the MNM-NÖK report (in relation to Surfer files) are the issues of closed or proprietary data formats and the common use of proprietary software within geophysical survey. In addition to simply storing data in an accessible and sustainable format, geophysical survey data also requires detailed metadata in order to record how the survey was undertaken, any problems or issues encountered during the survey, and how the resulting dataset has been processed. A combination of accessible file formats and metadata is key to the continued preservation and accessibility of geophysical datasets.

As with excavation datasets, the combination of expertise in terms of data creation, field experience, and data storage among the ARIADNE partners offers the potential to expand and develop existing guidelines through the referencing and synchronising of existing and new guidelines i.e. those developed by ADS, DAI, and DANS, and those forthcoming through the ArchaeoLandscapes project. In addition, where partners have expertise in carrying out geophysical survey and have specified an interest in improving or developing guidance, there is the potential to develop a number of case studies applying existing guidelines to relevant datasets.

3.5 Aerial Survey Data: Lidar and photography

Aerial survey data, incorporating aerial photography (either born-digital or digitised) and Lidar (airborne laser scanning) data, has also been highlighted as an area of both expertise and for further guidance development.

Currently the situation, particularly in regard to preserving Lidar data, is that there is little developed guidance beyond that detailing the data collection phase. This is less the case for aerial photography – which has a long history of use in archaeology for many countries – but new digital techniques and capture methods have introduced various new issues (e.g. file formats and metadata) alongside new applications (e.g. GIS). The introduction of small-scale capture methods such as UAVs alongside new methods for capturing both photography and lidar data together highlight that, as previously

discussed with geophysical survey, aerial survey data can be both technically challenging and incorporate a variety of practice.

As with geophysical survey data, a similar situation is evident with regard to aerial photography and Lidar data. A number of partners are actively involved in the capture of aerial survey data (Discovery Programme and ZRC-SAZU) while others such as ADS and CYI-STARC are focussed more on the storage and dissemination of such datasets. ADS has produced and revised a set of guidelines focussed on aerial survey but these have limited discussion of file formats, particularly those for Lidar data, and require expansion in terms of data processing and documentation. Partners in the 3D-ICONS and ArchaeoLandscapes projects, specifically Discovery Programme and ZRC-SAZU are also currently working on guidelines for aerial survey data. CYI-STARC, also under the ArchaeoLandscapes project, are currently surveying aerial photography archives with a view to developing a descriptive metadata schema for this data type. Additionally, ARUP-CAS have specified an interest in providing input into the development of aerial photography guidance and it is likely that other partners (e.g. DANS and DAI) might also want to contribute.

3.6 3D Datasets

A number of partners have specified expertise in 3D datasets or a need for further development of guidance for this type of data. In addition to Lidar data discussed in the previous section, '3D data' is taken here to primarily include datasets resulting from techniques such as terrestrial laser scanning and photogrammetry together with a range of other models and computer visualisations derived from a number of acquisition methods.

ARIADNE partners involved with both the 3D-ICONS and ArchaeoLandscapes projects (ATHENA-CETI, CYI-STARC, Discovery Programme, and ZRC-SAZU) are currently involved in the production of guidelines for the creation, documentation, and preservation of 3D datasets. ADS currently has detailed guidance on documenting and preserving data from terrestrial laser scanning⁹⁹ and photogrammetry¹⁰⁰ but would benefit from additional guidance on preserving and disseminating 3D models and visualisations.

In terms of practice and data creation, both Discovery Programme and ZRC-SAZU are also involved in the acquisition of 3D data in the field. ATHENA-CETI, through Clepsydra, is also currently undertaking the 3D digitisation and modelling of both monuments and objects, and ARHEO similarly has expressed expertise in 3D field documentation and photogrammetry. CYI-STARC, while also involved in data creation, has been specifically developing a repository and research platform for the storage, dissemination and documentation (i.e. metadata schemas) of 3D objects.

The range of expertise and involvement evident from these ARIADNE partners appears to cover the complete lifecycle of 3D data from creation to archiving. Linking and referencing of existing and forthcoming guidelines would be beneficial for all partners and provide 'lifecycle' guidance for this type of dataset. Partners also appear to be well placed to provide case studies covering both the data creation and archiving stages.

3.7 Scientific Analysis and Dating

While not a major theme, a number of partner organisations have expressed an interest in developing and sharing best practice with regard to scientific techniques and dating methods. A key opportunity here is the development of a dendrochronology guide for archaeologists focussing on

⁹⁹ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/LaserScan_Toc

¹⁰⁰ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/Photogram_Toc

the new TRiDAS data standard (see Section 2.7). Interest in the development of this guide, led by DANS, has been expressed by both ATHENA-CETI and DAI. In addition, ATHENA-CETI has highlighted experience in a range of scientific techniques for the analysis and dating of archaeological material. The protocols which support these techniques may prove useful to other partners as the basis for understanding both sample collection and the interpretation of results.

3.8 Summary

The seven themes discussed above have emerged from the individual organisation reports detailed in Section 2 and form the basis for the contributions to the Guides to Good Practice discussed in Section 4, below (summarised in Table 3.1). While these themes cover the vast majority of areas in which good practice has been reported there are undoubtedly other, smaller, areas in which partner organisations have expertise and it is hoped that, through a collaborative approach to Task 4.6, these partners will come forward.

Additionally, these themes do not match on a one-to-one basis with the areas of contribution discussed in the subsequent section and the production of case studies and alignment of existing guidelines is planned to occur over a number of themed areas.

Table 3.1: Areas of expertise of the ARIADNE content providing partners.

N.B. Although this table highlights those areas of expertise and good practice reported by each organisation in Section 2 of this document, it does not reflect the level or extent of this expertise and does not provide a direct comparison of organisations.

	General Data Archiving and Repository	National Database (sites, monuments)	Excavation	Field Survey	Geophysics	Aerial Survey (photography and lidar)	3D Data	Dendrochronology	3D-ICONS Project	ArchaeoLandscapes Project (ArLand)
ADS	X	X	X	X	X	X				
ARHEO		X	X	X	X		X			
ARUP-CAS		X	X	X	X	X			X	
ATHENA-CETI							X	X	X	X
CYI-STARC	X					X	X		X	X
DAI	X							X		X
DANS	X		X	X				X		X
DISCOVERY					X	X	X		X	X
INRAP		X	X	X	X					
MiBACT-ICCU	X	X	X							
MNM-NÖK			X	X	X					
NIAM-BAS		X	X	X						
OEAW			X	X						
ZRC-SAZU		X	X	X		X	X			X

4 Future Work: Contributions to the Guides to Good Practice (Task 4.6)

4.1 Alignment and Referencing Between Existing Good Practice Documents

As highlighted in Section 3.1, the alignment and cross-referencing of existing guidelines, i.e. those held by ADS, DANS, and DAI, is a key area of work for Task 4.6. This will include the identification of gaps in current guidelines, where these can be filled by partner guidelines, and where translation may be beneficial for other partners (e.g. OEAW and DAI may both benefit from selected translation of guidelines).

4.2 Case Studies

The development of case studies applying relevant areas of existing Good Practice documents to specific data sets held by ARIADNE partners, for the purposes of testing relevance, highlighting deficiencies and areas for improvements, is seen as a beneficial area of work across the various themes and an area to which all partner organisations could contribute. As discussed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, such case studies may be particularly appropriate for partners looking to develop good practice in the storage and documentation of data associated with fieldwork and excavation, and may focus on either discrete excavation / site datasets or to larger collections of single types of data (e.g. digital reports or images) that accompany field work or collection focussed databases.

Additionally, case studies may be used to support the development, aligning and referencing of the wider guides as discussed in Section 4.1.

A number of such case studies, including one produced by DAI as part of ARIADNE Task 4.6, are currently available via the ADS Guides to Good Practice¹⁰¹.

4.3 ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D-ICONS Guidelines

As per Section 4.1 (above), the alignment and referencing of forthcoming Good Practice documents, specifically those being created under the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D-ICONS projects (as described in Sections 3.4 and 3.5) has been identified as an area to pursue under Task 4.6. New guidelines covering aerial survey (photography and Lidar) and geophysical survey should be referenced by, and synchronised with, current guidelines held by ADS, DANS, and DAI in order to provide a coherent and robust set of resources. Illustration of these best practices should be through the creation of case studies by those partners with expertise in the relevant methods (ARHEO, ARUP-CAS, CYI-STARC, Discovery Programme, Inrap, MNM-NÖK, NIAM-BAS, ZRC-SAZU).

4.4 3D Datasets

As described in Section 3.6, development of existing 3D guidelines – either through case studies or the extension of existing documents – should be pursued under Task 4.6. This development should ideally focus on the preservation, dissemination, and documentation of 3D models and visualisations i.e. areas where current guidelines require further development. Such development will primarily involve those partners also involved in the 3D-ICONS and ArchaeoLandscapes projects – particularly

¹⁰¹ http://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/CS_CaseStudiesToc

CYI-STARC – in collaboration with those partners involved in data archiving and repository operations (ADS, DANS, and DAI).

4.5 Dendrochronology Guide and Scientific Analysis

Production of a new dendrochronology guide led by DANS and authored by Prof. Esther Jansma and Peter Brewer was approved at the ARIADNE Steering Committee Meeting on 3 September, 2013 in Pilsen, and is currently underway. As the dating process is largely carried out by specialist labs, this guide will focus specifically on providing archaeologists with an understanding of the possibilities dendrochronological data has in the context of their research questions and what to expect in terms of data and documentation. It is expected that other partners (e.g. ADS, ATHENA-CETI, and DAI) will contribute feedback and guidance for the development of this guide.

Section 3.7 also highlights the possibility to extend this guidance, through the expertise of ATHENA-CETI, to other scientific methods of dating and analysis, specifically thermoluminescence dating and ceramic analysis.

5 Conclusion

The survey of ARIADNE partner organisations detailed in Section 2 has highlighted the existence of a range of guidance and Good Practice documents that reflect the diversity of the organisations themselves. As expected, such guidance documents reflect both an organisation's area of expertise and function and range from broad guidelines on data and report structures and the structure of national databases, through to guidelines and recommendations for excavation and fieldwork, and finally down to guidelines for specific survey (e.g. lidar) or data set types (e.g. 3D or dating techniques). In some cases these guidelines tie into wider guidance (e.g. CIDOC) or good practice projects such as ArchaeoLandscapes or 3D-ICONS.

This report has identified five broad themes (Section 4) that will form the basis for work to be carried out under Task 4.6 *Guides to Good Practice*, these are:

- The alignment and referencing of existing Good Practice documents.
- The creation of case studies illustrating the application of Good Practice documents to specific data sets for which no good practice currently exists.
- The referencing and incorporation of guidelines currently under production through the ArchaeoLandscapes and 3D-ICONS projects into existing guidelines and the illustration of these guidelines through relevant case studies.
- The revision, creation or enhancement of guidelines for 3D datasets.
- The creation of guidelines for data from scientific dating and analysis, specifically dendrochronological datasets.